

**AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE
SEMESTER EXAMINATION SYSTEM IMPLEMENTED AT THE
POSTGRADUATE LEVEL STUDENTS UNDER THE NATIONAL
EDUCATION POLICY 2020**

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Paper Received On: 21 October 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 25 November 2024

Published On: 01 December 2024

Abstract

Education is essential to achieve full human potential and contribute to national development. In the coming times, India will be the country with the largest youth population in the world. The task of providing quality education to these youth will depend on India. The objective of this new National Education Policy is to provide equal quality education and equality of educational opportunities. Instead of increasing the content of education, there is a need to emphasize that students learn to think logically and structurally and understand various subjects and the interrelationships of educational, social, economic, cultural and political. Many policy changes have been made in the education system in the National Education Policy 2020, the main objective of which is to achieve the goal of Sustainable Development Agenda 2030 set by the Government of India in 2015. In this new National Education Policy 2020, special emphasis has been given on continuous and comprehensive evaluation. In this process, in this new National Education Policy 2020, semester examination system has been implemented in all the state/private universities and colleges from the entrance level (first semester) in the courses up to postgraduate level from the session 2022-23. The vision of this new National Education Policy 2020 is to advance education filled with Indian values, due to which higher education will be of quality and equality of educational opportunities which will directly contribute to making India a world leader and global superpower.

Key -*Semester Examination System, National Education Policy 2020, Continuous and Comprehensive Assessment*

Introduction

Education is a discipline that elevates humans from animality to humanity. It acquaints individuals with society and helps them establish themselves within it. Through education, a person studies various aspects of society and strives to lead a successful life. (Patel, Surender & Verma, S K. 2024). Teachers have an important role to play in teaching as well as an integral component of our continuum of schooling. It is up to the teachers to establish critical fundamental skills, communication, attitudes, importance judgment and the correct adoption of our students. (Kumar, Pradeep & Verma, S K. 2024). With the help of examination system, the successes of the teacher and the learning processes are assessed. Therefore, it is very important to pay attention to the good quality of the examination system. Keeping this in mind, on the basis of various suggestions made from time to time by various commissions and education policies for improving the examination system, emphasis is being laid on the process of continuous and comprehensive evaluation. For this, the new National Education Policy 2020 has also given special emphasis on continuous and comprehensive evaluation in its report. In the new National Education Policy 2020, the semester examination system has been implemented in postgraduate courses in all state/private universities and colleges from the session 2022-23. Semester Examination System – In our country, a session of a class usually lasts for one year and at the end of it there is an examination. In the universities of India, on the basis of European universities, there is a system of dividing one year's session into two equal sessions of six months each, studying and examining one session in the first six months and studying and examining the other session in the second six months. . Thus, the three-year undergraduate course is divided into six equal semesters and the two-year Masters course is divided into four equal semesters. This type of system is called semester system. In this system, if a candidate fails in a question paper of any semester, then he is not failed but is given admission in the next semester and he is given an opportunity to re-study the failed question paper and improve from it. Re-examine in that question paper in the same semester. But there is some variation in the rules of this system of different universities. In the semester system, learning units are created first. After this, each unit is divided into credits, that is, it is decided in how many periods a part of a unit will be completed. One credit contains approximately enough course work to be completed in the prescribed semester time using 50-60 minutes of classroom instruction and 2-3 hours of homework per week. In this system, students are able to complete credits only if they attend prescribed theory classes,

complete practical work, obtain minimum marks in internal assessments and pass the semester-end examination. Following are the advantages and objectives of semester examination system – This examination system provides opportunity for continuous learning, evaluation and feedback. Through this system students develop better understanding of the subject. This system provides an opportunity for better interaction between the student and the teacher. It develops skills, knowledge etc. of the students. In this system the entire academic curriculum is also divided into two parts, so students neither feel burdened by extensive or long curriculum nor do they feel monotony. To promote creative thinking among students. To develop the ability of analysis, critical thinking, and conceptual clarity in students. The National Education Policy 2020 aims to comprehensively reform the Indian education system, bringing education in line with Indian values, with a focus on quality and equity. Under this policy, semester examination system has been implemented in all courses of higher education to ensure continuous and comprehensive assessment of students. The goal of this system is to promote the process of continuous improvement and development in education.

Study of Related Literature

Hussain and Habiwa (2009) Conducted a study on 'Improving the evaluation process of learners' and as a result, 90 percent of teachers supported the semester system instead of annual evaluation to increase the achievement of learners, which gives students more opportunity to learn and can get.

Munshi, Javed and Hussain (2012) Conducted a study on the topic 'Examination in Semester System: Observation of Faculty and Students'. For the research, a small sample consisting of 270 students and 45 teachers from different departments of Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan was taken to represent all the departments of the university. A 34 item questionnaire was given on the Linkert scale. And as a result it was observed that most of the students disagreed with the semester examination system due to many shortcomings like bias, prejudice and subjectivity. On the contrary, teachers' perception was in favor of the semester system.

Rahman (2013) Conducted a research study involving 133 randomly selected postgraduate students and 44 teachers in Attitude of students and teachers towards semester system: A study in some selected degree colleges of Nagaon Town, Nagaon district of Assam. Did. A self-structured questionnaire was administered revealing the perception towards five

dimensions of the semester system – curriculum-course coverage, regularity of classes, teacher and teaching methods, evaluation and feedback and availability of resources. The data collected were analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The result found that students' attitude towards internal assessment and overall assessment is not quite satisfactory.

Singh and Jha (2013) Conducted a comparative study on anxiety, hope and interest among students of private medical and engineering colleges. The objective of the study was to assess the level of optimism and anxiety and its relationship with academic achievement among medical and engineering students. A total of 346 students (171 medical and 175 engineering) from 3 medical and 4 engineering colleges of Uttar Pradesh were taken. Anxiety and optimism were tested using Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety Test (SCAT-2007) and Learned Optimism Scale (LO5-2000) instruments respectively. And as a result, it was observed that there was a negative relationship between anxiety and optimism and academic achievement, whereas there was a positive relationship between hope and academic achievement.

Mishra (2014) Studied the impact of teaching aids on students' academic achievement and retention in school. The objective of the study was to know the effect of educational attainment, school retention status and teaching aids. In the sample, 120 students of class 5 in government primary schools of Shahjahanpur city area were selected. The findings found that the availability of educational resources in schools is negligible. Students who use educational aids have better interest than students who do not use educational aids.

Dangi, Navraj (2016) Conducted a study on 'Attitude of girl students towards semester system implementation'. This research aimed to find out the attitudes of students towards semester system implementation. The data obtained from 120 students was arranged, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted by the researcher using statistics like mean and chi-square test. And it was observed that students have a positive attitude towards the semester system.

Bista (2016) Conducted a study on the topic 'Teachers' opinion towards semester system in mathematics education. The researcher chose a mixed approach, sequential and exploratory work. By involving mathematics teachers in the research, the data were analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. For this, a scale related to the questionnaire and interview guidelines was used. In the conclusion it was seen that the teachers have positive opinion towards the semester system.

Imran , Mohammad & Verma , S K (2019). Stated that parental involvement at home motivates and helps in doing all the school based assignments, projects, home work and varies activities and conclude that parental involvement at home as well as school plays a key role in child's academic success.

Surendra and Anand (2019) 'B.Ed. Study of trainees' attitude towards semester system of curriculum: Worked on case study, under this he studied B.Ed. conducted by Allahabad University. Three colleges of fourth semester of B.Sc. were selected as sample through purposive sampling method and survey method was used in this study. Data were collected by the researcher by directly contacting the students using a self-made questionnaire and the conclusion was that B.Ed. It is a training program that requires not just classroom teaching but extensive training. Of course this training is based on a detailed outline. It is not possible to achieve the objectives of this teacher education course by evaluating it once in a session. Its complete training is possible only in the semester system and the quality of the semester system is being reflected in the feedback given by the students.

Paudel (2019). Studied the attitude of university teachers towards the English language curriculum of M.Ed. An explanatory sequential mixed research design was employed in this study. Forty-five English language teachers were selected from affiliated campuses of Tribhuvan University, Nepal for the research. The research shows that university English teachers had positive attitudes towards the current curriculum thanks to their input and process.

Jang, Kim & Kim (2020) 'Explored the perceived impact of low academic achievement after free semester in Korean middle schools' by some Korean parents and students regarding no exams during FS (exam free semester). Expressed concern. Thus, this study explored whether FS affects student achievement by estimating the average population treatment effect of FS policy on academic achievement in Seoul schools. Based on the inverse probability of treatment weights (IPTW) approach with existing empirical data, it was observed that overall, no significant difference in academic achievement was observed between pilot FS schools and non-FS schools.

Dixit and Sunil (2021) Studied on the topic 'Comparative study of the attitude of teachers and students of Arts Faculty towards the semester education system run by Lucknow University. In this research study, students were randomly selected from four selected degree colleges affiliated to Lucknow University. It was conducted on fifty graduate students and fifty

graduate teachers so that a comparative study of their attitude towards the semester system recently implemented by the university could be done. The data collected through a self-constructed attitude scale towards the five dimensions of the semester system - curriculum, curriculum coverage, regularity of classes, teachers and teaching, evaluation and feedback methods and availability of resources - were analyzed using percentage, mean, standard deviation and two median values. The significance of the difference has been determined using statistical methods. Research results have shown that students' perception towards internal assessment and overall assessment is not quite satisfactory. Most of the respondents also do not understand the evaluation in CGPA. The study revealed lack of necessary resources, especially information resources, in degree colleges to make the semester system effective and successful.

Choi and Eom (2022) Studied on the topic 'A study of the effects of the open semester system on academic achievement and career'. For this, longitudinal study data from Heart 2013 was used. Performed the difference-in-difference (DID) method for data analysis. Additionally, the quantile DID method was used to examine whether the effects of the open semester system differ across the distribution of academic achievement and career maturity. The results found for the first time a significant positive impact of the open semester system on the academic achievement of middle school students. The findings of the present study thus necessitate the development of strategies by all stakeholders to arrange minimum resources and facilities, which have a direct impact on student achievement.

Patel, Surendra & Verma, S K. (2023). Increasing Trend of Technology Usage among Secondary School Teachers in Accordance with the National Education Policy 2020. The objective of this research is to understand the growing interest among teachers in using technology for teaching following the COVID-19 pandemic and the National Education Policy 2020. The study aims to explore how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can be utilized to make the teaching-learning process more engaging and effective. A descriptive research method was employed, with a survey method selected for data collection. A self-constructed questionnaire was used to gather data, and hypothesis testing was conducted using mean, standard deviation, and T-test. The findings of the research indicate that the use of ICT by teachers in teaching has a positive impact on the academic achievement of secondary-level students.

Kumar, Narendra & Verma, S K. (2023). A Study of the Impact of Family Environment on the Study Habits of Students in Upper Primary Schools Based on Government and Non-Government School. The family environment and study habits play a crucial role in a student's education and development. Both of these areas can contribute significantly to a student's progress, leading to their social, economic, and mental advancement. Support and encouragement within the family environment increase a child's self-support, which can lead to greater success in their studies. Learning ideal time management within the family setting can help children achieve excellence in their studies. The atmosphere of respect and thoughtfulness in the family can inspire children to study in new and thoughtful directions. Encouragement of a healthy lifestyle in the family can make children more responsible in their studies.

Rastogi, Seema (2024). Conducted study of Gender-Based Attitudes of Trainees towards Internship B.El.Ed. Curriculum and concluded that there is no significant differences in attitudes towards internship in B.El.Ed. Curriculum based on gender, both male and female trainees have similarly positive attitudes towards internship. The internship provides valuable real-world experience, which enhance their motivation and teaching skills.

Gupta, Keerti & Verma, S K. (2024) The modern era is the era of science. In which Digital India campaign is playing an important role in transforming the entire country into a strong society. A new education system in line with the ambitious goals of 21st century education will develop the necessary knowledge, values, attitudes, skills and abilities such as logical thinking, creativity, scientific thinking, ability to communicate and cooperate, multilingualism, problem solving, ethical thinking in the year 2020.

Kumar, Rajesh & Verma, S K. (2024). An Analytical Study of Study Habits in the Context of the Semester Examination System at Undergraduate Level Students under the National Education Policy 2020. International journal of research and analytical reviews. 11. 942-946. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a significant milestone in the field of education in India. This policy aims to bring about reforms at all levels of education. A key aspect of the NEP 2020 is the implementation of the semester education system, which affects students' study methods and habits. This study analyzes various aspects of the semester education system and its impact on students' study habits.

Conclusion

The National Education Policy 2020 is a step towards a significant change in the Indian education system. The semester examination system implemented in this policy focuses on holistic development, critical thinking, and competency-based education of the students. National Education Policy 2020 is bringing a revolution in Indian education. In which emphasis has been laid on critical thinking, thinking, holistic development and competency-based education. NEP 2020 aims to develop an education system that is more inclusive and learner-centric by changing the nature of tests and assessments. By moving away from rote learning and toward comprehensive assessment frameworks, teachers can help students gain deeper knowledge of their subjects, inspire creativity, and develop important life skills. Although these ideas may be difficult to implement, their long-term benefits for students and society make it worthwhile. The National Education Policy 2020 paves the way for a time where tests accurately represent the capabilities of students, enabling them to prosper and make valuable contributions in an ever-changing world. The semester examination system implemented in the National Education Policy 2020 guides towards a future where the education system is able to showcase the true capabilities of students, enabling them to contribute significantly to society.

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